

Column	Description
id	Unique identifier for each participant
연령(만):숫자만 기입	Age in years
성별:남성(1),여성(2)	Gender: Male (1), Female (2)
직업	Occupation
학력	Education
이명방향	Tinnitus direction
이명발병기간 (개월수로 계산하여 숫자만 기입)	Duration of tinnitus in months
스트레스	Stress level
불면증상	Insomnia symptoms
정신과방문경험	History of Visiting a Psychiatrist
수면약복용여부	Use of sleeping medication
THI1F:1-3점 으로 변환	Responses to the THI test were converted to a 1-3 scale.
THI2F	Responses to the THI test were converted to a 1-3 scale.
THI3E	Responses to the THI test were converted to a 1-3 scale.
THI4F	Responses to the THI test were converted to a 1-3 scale.
THI5C	Responses to the THI test were converted to a 1-3 scale.
THI6E	Responses to the THI test were converted to a 1-3 scale.
THI7F	Responses to the THI test were converted to a 1-3 scale.
THI8C	Responses to the THI test were converted to a 1-3 scale.
THI9F	Responses to the THI test were converted to a 1-3 scale.
THI10E	Responses to the THI test were converted to a 1-3 scale.
THI11C	Responses to the THI test were converted to a 1-3 scale.
THI12F	Responses to the THI test were converted to a 1-3 scale.
THI13F	Responses to the THI test were converted to a 1-3 scale.
THI14E	Responses to the THI test were converted to a 1-3 scale.
THI15F	Responses to the THI test were converted to a 1-3 scale.
THI16E	Responses to the THI test were converted to a 1-3 scale.
THI17E	Responses to the THI test were converted to a 1-3 scale.
THI18F	Responses to the THI test were converted to a 1-3 scale.
THI19C	Responses to the THI test were converted to a 1-3 scale.
THI20F	Responses to the THI test were converted to a 1-3 scale.
THI21E	Responses to the THI test were converted to a 1-3 scale.
THI22E	Responses to the THI test were converted to a 1-3 scale.
THI23C	Responses to the THI test were converted to a 1-3 scale.
THI24F	Responses to the THI test were converted to a 1-3 scale.
THI25E	Responses to the THI test were converted to a 1-3 scale.
BDI1:1-4으로 변환	Responses to the BDI test were converted to a 1-4 scale.
BDI2	Responses to the BDI test were converted to a 1-4 scale.
BDI3	Responses to the BDI test were converted to a 1-4 scale.
BDI4	Responses to the BDI test were converted to a 1-4 scale.
BDI5	Responses to the BDI test were converted to a 1-4 scale.

BDI6	Responses to the BDI test were converted to a 1-4 scale.
BDI7	Responses to the BDI test were converted to a 1-4 scale.
BDI8	Responses to the BDI test were converted to a 1-4 scale.
BDI9	Responses to the BDI test were converted to a 1-4 scale.
BDI10	Responses to the BDI test were converted to a 1-4 scale.
BDI11	Responses to the BDI test were converted to a 1-4 scale.
BDI12	Responses to the BDI test were converted to a 1-4 scale.
BDI13	Responses to the BDI test were converted to a 1-4 scale.
BDI14	Responses to the BDI test were converted to a 1-4 scale.
BDI15	Responses to the BDI test were converted to a 1-4 scale.
BDI16	Responses to the BDI test were converted to a 1-4 scale.
BDI17	Responses to the BDI test were converted to a 1-4 scale.
BDI18	Responses to the BDI test were converted to a 1-4 scale.
BDI19	Responses to the BDI test were converted to a 1-4 scale.
음식체중조절여부	Values of 1 or 2 were recorded for dietary weight control.
BDI20	Responses to the BDI test were converted to a 1-4 scale.
BDI21	Responses to the BDI test were converted to a 1-4 scale.
AAQ1:1-7으로 변환	Responses to the AAQ test were converted to a 1-7 scale.
AAQ2	Responses to the AAQ test were converted to a 1-7 scale.
AAQ3	Responses to the AAQ test were converted to a 1-7 scale.
AAQ4	Responses to the AAQ test were converted to a 1-7 scale.
AAQ5	Responses to the AAQ test were converted to a 1-7 scale.
AAQ6	Responses to the AAQ test were converted to a 1-7 scale.
AAQ7	Responses to the AAQ test were converted to a 1-7 scale.
AAQ8	Responses to the AAQ test were converted to a 1-7 scale.
AAQ9	Responses to the AAQ test were converted to a 1-7 scale.
AAQ10	Responses to the AAQ test were converted to a 1-7 scale.
PSQI1	Responses to the PSQI test were recorded as scores.
PSQI2	Responses to the PSQI test were recorded as scores.
PSQI3	Responses to the PSQI test were recorded as scores.
PSQI4	Responses to the PSQI test were recorded as scores.
PSQI5_A	Responses to the PSQI test were recorded as scores.
PSQI5_B	Responses to the PSQI test were recorded as scores.
PSQI5_C	Responses to the PSQI test were recorded as scores.
PSQI5_D	Responses to the PSQI test were recorded as scores.
PSQI5_E	Responses to the PSQI test were recorded as scores.
PSQI5_F	Responses to the PSQI test were recorded as scores.
PSQI5_G	Responses to the PSQI test were recorded as scores.
PSQI5_H	Responses to the PSQI test were recorded as scores.
PSQI5_I	Responses to the PSQI test were recorded as scores.
PSQI5_J	Responses to the PSQI test were recorded as scores.
PSQ-6	Responses to the PSQI test were recorded as scores.
PSQ-7	Responses to the PSQI test were recorded as scores.

PSQ-8	Responses to the PSQI test were recorded as scores.
PSQ-9	Responses to the PSQI test were recorded as scores.
PSQ-10	Responses to the PSQI test were recorded as scores.
PSQ-10A	Responses to the PSQI test were recorded as scores.
PSQ-10B	Responses to the PSQI test were recorded as scores.
PSQ-10C	Responses to the PSQI test were recorded as scores.
PSQ-10D	Responses to the PSQI test were recorded as scores.
PSQ-10E	Responses to the PSQI test were recorded as scores.